

Supplementary Material for “The Short, The Pragmatic, and The Toxic: Stylometric Roles in Social Media Influence”

09/16/2025

Appendix A: Training Weights of Stylometric Features From Stance Classification Model

Appendix B: t-SNE Visualization of Users by Stylometric Features, Reduced to 2D

Appendix C: Stance Model Code

<https://github.com/ckan0321/stylometric-stance-modeling>